

Limitations of Solubility Method for Determining Dissociation Constant.

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The solubility of sparingly soluble acid is increased in a solution of sodium salt of a weak acid is well known, and the quantitative measurements of the actual increase have been made by Noyes and Chappin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 442), Philip (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 987), Philip and Garner (*ibid.*, 1909, 95, 1466) and by Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 807).

Noyes (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 273) has deduced an equation from which the solubility of a sparingly soluble acid in the sodium salts of weak acids can be calculated. Dhar (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 800) has deduced a formula for finding out the dissociation constant of weak acids. He has shown that if 'a', be the solubility of the weak acid in water, K_1 , its dissociation constant, 'b', the solubility of the acid in the concentration 'c', of the sodium salt of the weak acid whose dissociation constant K_2 is required then,

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \times a (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

Dhar and Dutta (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, 19, 407) have shown that this formula is applicable for very low concentrations of sodium salts. They have employed the solubility results of Philip (*loc. cit.*), and Philip and Garner (*loc. cit.*) for this purpose. All the acids considered by them were monobasic. This work was extended to dibasic acid as carbonic acid with whose help the dissociation constant of the acid of the sodium salt was determined. Datta and Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 824) observed that the above equation has to be modified and they showed

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \times a [c - 2(b - a)]}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

The applicability of the equation (1) has been verified also by Bhagwat and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 806) in case of numerous acids and they have shown that equation (2) is incorrect and the general formula for finding the dissociation constant when

the basicity of sparingly soluble acid is n , has been deduced, taking into consideration the degrees of ionisation of salts and acids in solution. Thus,

$$K_2 = \frac{nK_1 (1 - K_3) \times a [nK_2 c - K_4 (b - a)]}{K_5 \times K_4 (b - a)^2} \dots (3)$$

If we introduce the conception that the salts are completely ionised and acids do not ionise at all then,

$$K_2 = \frac{nK_1 \times a [nc - (b - a)]}{(b - a)^2} \dots \dots (4)$$

In this paper we have fully considered the limit of the concentration of sodium salt up to which these formulae hold and explanation has been forwarded for the deviations observed. For this purpose we have varied the concentrations of sodium salts over a very wide range and the results are recorded in the following tables.

A. Dissociation Constant of Formic Acid.

With benzoic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of benzoic acid = 6.4×10^{-5} at 30°. $a = 0.03306$.

a .	b .	$b - a$.	$c - b + a$.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2}$.
0.0596	0.05196	0.01890	0.04072	2.3×10^{-4}
0.0855	0.05708	0.02402	0.06548	2.3
0.1790	0.06889	0.03583	0.1431	2.26
0.3158	0.08064	0.04758	0.2682	2.4
0.4211	0.08951	0.05645	0.3646	2.3
0.6316	0.1008	0.056774	0.5639	2.49
1.2355	0.1340	0.1009	1.1346	2.26
1.6474	0.1466	0.1135	1.5338	2.4
2.4711	0.1666	0.1335	2.3375	2.6

It will be seen from these results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.0596 N to 2.4711N or from 4.0541 g. to 168.0356 g. per litre), although there is a tendency to increase for the value of the dissociation constant when concentration of the sodium salt increases.

With salicylic acid at 30°. K_1 of salicylic acid = 1.6×10^{-3} at 25°. $a = 0.01987$.

c.	b.	b-a.	c-b+a.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.
0.06892	0.06248	0.04261	0.02571	2.81×10^{-4}
0.1008	0.07501	0.05514	0.4567	2.98
0.1929	0.0875	0.06769	0.6468	2.8
0.1924	0.1097	0.08989	0.1026	2.52
0.3528	0.1525	0.1326	0.2202	2.48
0.4887	0.1913	0.1714	0.3173	2.1
0.5292	0.1961	0.1762	0.3530	2.25
0.7056	0.2325	0.2126	0.5930	2.61
1.0585	0.2925	0.2726	0.7858	2.1
2.1170	0.4614	0.4415	1.6755	1.7

It will be seen from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.06832N to 2.1170N or from 4.6456 g. to 144.0145 g. per litre), although there is a tendency to decrease the value of dissociation constant as the concentration of the sodium salt increases.

B. Dissociation Constant of Acetic Acid.

With benzoic acid at 30°. K_1 of benzoic acid at 30° = 6.4×10^{-5} . $a = 0.03306$.

c.	b.	b-a.	c-b+a.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.
0.09282	0.06107	0.0280	0.00482	1.25×10^{-5}
0.06565	0.08196	0.0489	0.01675	1.42
0.08128	0.0909	0.05784	0.02344	1.42
0.1067	0.1010	0.06794	0.03874	1.7
0.1739	0.1326	0.09951	0.07446	1.5
0.2008	0.1452	0.11214	0.08967	1.46
0.2475	0.1603	0.1272	0.1220	1.53
0.3413	0.1896	0.1565	0.1848	1.52
0.4267	0.2121	0.1790	0.2477	1.57
0.4950	0.2260	0.1990	0.3020	1.64
0.7425	0.2755	0.2425	0.5000	1.72
0.9000	0.3145	0.2815	0.7065	1.81
1.4850	0.3949	0.3618	1.1292	1.74

It will be seen from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.03282N to 1.4850N or from 2.2322 g. to 201.9644 g. per litre), although there is a tendency to increase the value of the dissociation constant as the concentration of the sodium salt increases.

With salicylic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of salicylic acid = 1.0×10^{-3} at 25°. $a = 0.01987$.

$c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$a-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$
0.01731	0.03499	0.01512	0.00219	1.9×10^{-4}
0.02597	0.04375	0.02388	0.00109	7.2×10^{-5}
0.05194	6.06625	0.04638	0.00556	5.1
0.07666	0.0850	0.06513	0.01154	5.4
0.14636	0.1400	0.1201	0.02623	2.87
0.2683	0.2250	0.2151	0.06321	2.99
0.3220	0.2625	0.2426	0.07937	2.68
0.5366	0.4150	0.3951	0.1415	1.81
0.8050	0.5611	0.5412	0.2638	1.78
1.610	1.0680	1.0481	0.5618	1.02

It will be seen from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is practically of the same order between the range investigated (from 0.01731N to 1.61N or from 2.3547 g. to 218.9932 g. per litre) and gradually decreases as the concentration of the sodium salt is increased.

With cinnamic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of cinnamic acid at 25° = 3.51×10^{-5} . $a = 0.004688$.

$c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$c-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$
0.01731	0.01191	0.00722	0.01009	3.18×10^{-5}
0.02597	0.01577	0.01108	0.01488	1.99
0.05194	0.01964	0.01495	0.03698	2.72
0.07666	0.02381	0.01912	0.05754	2.59
0.1463	0.03274	0.02805	0.1183	2.46
0.2634	0.04435	0.03966	0.2286	2.44
0.3220	0.04881	0.04412	0.2278	2.34
0.5366	0.06100	0.05721	0.4794	2.41
0.3050	0.07501	0.07032	0.7346	2.39
1.6100	0.1244	0.1197	1.5903	1.82

It will be seen from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.01731N to 1.61N or from 2.3574 g. to 218.9932 g. per litre), although there is a tendency to decrease the value of dissociation constant as the concentration of the sodium salt increases.

C. *Dissociation Constant of Citric Acid.*

With benzoic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of benzoic acid = 6.4×10^{-5} at 30°. $a = 0.03306$.

c .	b .	$b-a$.	$c-b+a$.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.
0.04512	0.06152	0.02846	0.01666	4.3×10^{-5}
0.06666	0.07308	0.04202	0.02664	4.2
0.12717	0.10260	0.06954	0.05763	2.5
0.23313	0.14170	0.10864	0.1245	2.27
0.27978	0.1577	0.12464	0.1531	1.78
0.4662	0.2051	0.1720	0.2942	1.67
0.6996	0.2475	0.2144	0.4652	2.23
0.9324	0.2793	0.2462	0.6862	2.45
1.3989	0.3205	0.2874	1.1117	2.85

It will be seen from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.04512N to 1.3989N or from 5.3701 g. to 166.4754 g. per litre), although the value of dissociation constant first decreases and then increases with the increase of the concentration of the salt.

With salicylic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of salicylic acid = 1.0×10^{-3} at 25°. $a = 0.01987$.

c .	b .	$b-a$.	$c-b+a$.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.
0.04512	0.05706	0.03719	0.00793	1.14×10^{-4}
0.06666	0.07435	0.05448	0.1218	8.19×10^{-5}
0.12717	0.1152	0.09543	0.3174	6.93
0.23313	0.1807	0.1608	0.07233	5.56
0.27978	0.2154	0.1955	0.08428	4.38
0.4662	0.3128	0.2929	0.1733	4.01
0.6996	0.4141	0.3942	0.3054	3.90
0.9324	0.5211	0.5012	0.4312	3.41
1.3989	0.6577	0.6378	0.7611	3.72

It will be clear from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is practically of the same order, between the range examined (from 0.04512N to 1.3989N or from 5.3701 g. to 166.4754 g. per litre). Clearly there is a tendency to decrease the dissociation constant as the concentration of the sodium salt increases.

With cinnamic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant K_1 of cinnamic acid = 3.51×10^{-5} at 25°. $a = 0.0046875$.

$c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$c-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}.$
0.04512	0.02344	0.01875	0.02637	1.23×10^{-4}
0.06666	0.02917	0.02448	0.04218	1.16
0.12717	0.04271	0.03802	0.08915	1.01
0.23313	0.05729	0.05260	0.1805	1.1
0.27978	0.06353	0.05884	0.2209	1.05
0.4662	0.07812	0.07343	0.3927	1.2
0.6996	0.08646	0.08177	0.6178	1.5
0.9324	0.09246	0.08777	0.8446	1.8
1.3989	0.09790	0.09932	1.3057	2.5

It will be clear from the above results that the value of dissociation constant is more or less constant over a wide range (from 0.04512N to 1.3982N or from 5.3701 g. to 166.4754 g. per litre), although there is a tendency to increase the dissociation constant as the concentration of the salt increases.

D. Dissociation Constant of Benzoic Acid.

With cinnamic acid at 16.3°. Dissociation constant K_1 of cinnamic acid = 3.51×10^{-5} at 25°. $a = 0.002643$.

$b.$	$b-a.$	$c-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}.$
0.01201	0.005288	0.002645	1.24×10^{-4}
0.02403	0.006901	0.004258	1.01×10^{-4}
0.04805	0.009410	0.006767	8.36×10^{-5}
0.1201	0.01399	0.01135	7.63
0.24028	0.02025	0.01761	6.65
0.4004	0.02845	0.02581	5.22
0.6007	0.03459	0.03195	5.17
0.9009	0.03763	0.03499	5.81

It will be clear from the above results that the value of dissociation constant steadily decreases with the increase of the concentration. The concentration of sodium benzoate ranges from 0.01201N to 0.8009N or from 1.7306 g. to 115.3737 g. per litre.

With salicylic acid at 14.5°. Dissociation constant K_1 of salicylic acid = 9.5×10^{-4} at 20°. $a = 0.01209$.

$c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$c-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$
0.01201	0.01758	0.00549	0.00652	2.48×10^{-3}
0.02402	0.02459	0.01250	0.01152	8.47
0.04804	0.02774	0.01565	0.03239	1.52
0.1201	0.03022	0.01813	0.01020	3.56
0.2402	0.03035	0.01826	0.02219	7.64
0.4003	0.03215	0.02006	0.3802	1.09×10^{-2}
0.6005	0.03105	0.01896	0.5815	1.86
0.8006	0.03270	0.02061	0.7799	2.11
1.201	0.03956	0.02747	1.1735	2.58

It will be clear from the above results that the value of dissociation constant gradually increases with the increase of the concentration. The concentration of the sodium benzoate ranges from 0.01201N to 1.201N or from 1.7306 g. to 173.0606 g. per litre.

E. Dissociation Constant of Salicylic Acid.

With benzoic acid at 30°. Dissociation constant of K_1 of benzoic acid = 6.2×10^{-5} at 30°. $a = 0.03306$.

$c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$c-b+a.$	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a (c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$
0.05889	0.03339	0.00099	0.05856	1.14×10^{-1}
0.08693	0.03485	0.00179	0.08514	5.6×10^{-2}
0.1659	0.00124	0.00818	0.1578	4.99×10^{-3}
0.3043	0.04742	0.01436	0.2899	2.97×10^{-3}
0.3651	0.05498	0.02182	0.3438	1.6×10^{-3}
0.4564	0.05912	0.02606	0.4803	1.34×10^{-3}
0.6085	0.08333	0.05027	0.5582	4.67×10^{-4}
0.9128	0.1125	0.07947	0.8334	2.79×10^{-4}
1.217	0.1805	0.1475	1.0695	1.04×10^{-4}
1.8255	0.2764	0.2433	1.5822	5.66×10^{-5}

It will be clear from the above results that the formula does not give constant value for K_2 . The values of dissociation constant decrease with the increase of concentration of the sodium salicylate. The concentration of sodium salicylate ranges from 0.05889N to 1.8255N or from 9.4220 g. to 292.08 g. per litre.

With succinic acid at 84.3°. Dissociation constant K_1 of succinic acid = 6.6×10^{-5} at 25°. $a = 0.8515$.

c .	b .	$b-a$.	$c-b+a$.	$K_2 = \frac{K_1 a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$.
0.07238	1.0000	0.1485	Negative	...
0.1882	1.0820	0.2305	"	...
0.2533	1.2030	0.3515	"	...
0.5066	1.4060	0.5545	"	...
0.7600	1.5880	0.7365	"	...
1.0133	1.6580	0.8065	0.0235	2.43×10^{-4}
1.5200	1.4710	0.6195	0.2068	1.79×10^{-6}
			0.9005	1.32×10^{-5}

It will be seen from the above results that the values of $c-b+a$ are negative or the formula for determining dissociation constant breaks down completely in this case, although at very high concentration we get positive results. The concentration of the salt ranges from 0.07238N to 1.52N or from 11.58 g. to 243.2 g. per litre.

DISCUSSION.

All the workers mentioned above have not taken into consideration the hydrolysis of these salts of weak acid and in this discussion we have fully studied the various types of equilibria which can exist and the various relations obtained from their considerations.

Let us consider an acid, say, C_6H_5COOH which is a weak acid and its solubility in water ' a '. Let us also consider the sodium salt of another weak acid, say, acetic acid and let the solubility of benzoic acid in the concentration ' c ', of the sodium acetate ' b '. Then under equilibrium we have,

The salts CH_3COONa and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}$ being those of weak acid partly hydrolyse, thus

Hence the hydrolytic constant K_7 of CH_3COONa is given by

$$K_7 = \frac{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}][\text{NaOH}]}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}][\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (\text{iv})$$

where $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]$, $[\text{NaOH}]$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]$, etc., represent the concentrations of CH_3COOH , NaOH , CH_3COONa etc., in equilibrium.

The equilibrium concentration of water being constant we can write

$$K_8 = \frac{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}][\text{NaOH}]}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (\text{v})$$

where $K_8 = K_7 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. Similarly, if K_9 is the hydrolytic constant of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}$

$$K_9 = \frac{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}][\text{NaOH}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (\text{vi})$$

where $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}]$, $[\text{NaOH}]$, etc., represent the concentrations of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$, NaOH , etc.

But the equation (i) being in equilibrium with the equations (ii) and (iii) they must be simultaneously satisfied.

$$\text{From (v) we have } [\text{NaOH}] = \frac{K_8 [\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{vii})$$

$$\text{From (vi) we have } [\text{NaOH}] = \frac{K_9 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{viii})$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{K_8 [\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]}{[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]} = \frac{K_9 [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}]}$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{K_8}{K_9} = K = \frac{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COONa}][\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}][\text{CH}_3\text{COONa}]} \quad \dots \quad (\text{ix})$$

From the equation (i) it is clear that in equilibrium the concentrations of C_6H_5COOH , CH_3COONa , CH_3COOH and C_6H_5COONa are respectively a , $c - b + a$, $b - a$, and $b - a$.

$$\text{Hence, } K = \frac{K_8}{K_9} = \frac{(c - b + a) \times a}{(b - a)} \quad \dots \quad (x)$$

Moreover, $NaOH$ ionises completely. Therefore the concentration of $[OH]$ is given by

$$[OH] = \frac{K_9(c - b + a)}{(b - a)} \quad \dots \quad (xi)$$

$$= \frac{K_9(b - a)}{a} \quad \dots \quad (xii)$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{[C_6H_5COO][H]}{[C_6H_5COOH]} = K_{10} \quad \dots \quad (xv)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{[CH_3COO][H]}{[CH_3COOH]} = K_{11} \quad \dots \quad (xvi)$$

where K_{10} and K_{11} are the dissociation constants of the acids. But according to the equation (i) the equations (xv) and (xvi) must be simultaneously satisfied. Hence,

$$\frac{K_{11}}{K_{10}} = \frac{[CH_3COO][C_6H_5COOH]}{[CH_3COOH][C_6H_5COO]}$$

Assuming that salts ionise completely and the weak acids do not ionise at all we get

$$\frac{K_{11}}{K_{10}} = \frac{(c - b + a) \times a}{(b - a)^2} \quad \dots \quad (xvii)$$

$$\text{Moreover, } [H] = \frac{K_{10}[C_6H_5COOH]}{[C_6H_5COO]} = \frac{K_{11}[CH_3COOH]}{[CH_3COO]}$$

$$[\text{H}] = \frac{K_{10} \times a}{b-a} = \frac{K_{11}(b-a)}{c-b+a} \quad \dots \quad (\text{xviii})$$

Also water ionises as $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{H} + \text{OH} \quad \dots \quad (\text{xix})$

or $[\text{H}] \cdot [\text{OH}] = K_w \quad \dots \quad (\text{xx})$

where K_w is the ionisation constant of water. From equations (xviii) and (xii) we have

$$\frac{K_{10} \times a}{b-a} \times \frac{K_9(b-a)}{a} = K_w \quad \text{or} \quad K_{10}K_9 = K_w \quad \dots \quad (\text{xxi})$$

and $K_{11}K_8 = K_w \quad \dots \quad (\text{xxii})$ [from equations (xviii) and (xi)].

Hence, $\frac{K_{10}}{K_8} = \frac{K_{11}}{K_9} \quad \dots \quad (\text{xxiii}) \quad \text{or,} \quad \frac{K_{10}}{K_{11}} = \frac{K_8}{K_9}$

which also follows from the equations (xvii) and (x). These equations show that the formulae for determining dissociation constant show maximum accuracy when the dissociation constants of the acid investigated and of the acid employed are identical or more or less of the same order. It will be seen from the results that the conclusion is borne out by the experiments.

Our results of the dissociation constant show that with benzoic acid the values of dissociation constant obtained, increases in case of formic and acetic acid as the concentration of sodium salt is increased. Similar is the case, for the values of dissociation constant of benzoic acid with salicylic acid, and citric acid with cinnamic acid. This may be explained from the view point that $(b-a)$, the rate of increase in solubility diminishes with the concentration of sodium salt, for with the increase in concentration of sodium salt the degree of hydrolysis of these salts diminishes and hence the amount of acid dissolved to balance this decrease.

However, the values of the dissociation constant with benzoic acid for salicylic acid goes on increasing with the dilution of the sodium salt. Same thing is observed for formic acid, acetic acid and citric acid with salicylic acid and for acetic acid and salicylic acid with cinnamic acid. In deducing the equation

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 \times a(c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$$

it has been shown that $(b-a)$ also represents the amount of undissociated acid. In this simple formula we have neglected the ionisation of the acid which increases with the dilution or the amount of undissociated molecules decreases. Therefore $(b-a)$ decreases with dilution and $(c-b+a)$ increases with dilution. It is therefore quite clear that K_2 should increase with dilution.

Thus it appears that there are two factors in these cases, the hydrolysis and ionisation and they act in reverse way. With the increase in concentration degree of hydrolysis decreases and therefore $(b-a)$, the increase in solubility diminishes while the degree of ionisation diminishes and hence the number of undissociated molecules or $(b-a)$ increases. Hence, according as one factor predominates over the other, the dissociation constant increases or decreases with the concentration of the sodium salt.

This conclusion seems to be supported by our observation of the values of dissociation constants of citric acid with benzoic acid.

It is more or less generally observed that weaker the acid, lower is the dissociation constant obtained. It has been shown by Bhagwat and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) that the cause of low dissociation constant for weaker acid is the greater hydrolysis of its sodium salt.

Our results for the dissociation constant of salicylic acid with succinic acid are negative at low concentration of the sodium salt when the simple formula is employed. But the succinic acid is dibasic and hence Bhagwat and Dhar's general formula should be applied. It is noteworthy to find that this formula gives positive results.

K_1 for succinic acid = 6.6×10^{-5} at 25° . $a = 0.8515$.

$2c.$	$b.$	$b-a.$	$(2c-b-a).$	$K_2 = \frac{2K_1 a (2c-b+a)}{(b-a)^2}$
0.2764	1.0820	0.2305	0.0459	6.11×10^{-5}
0.5066	1.2030	0.3515	0.1551	7.05
1.0132	1.4060	0.5545	0.4487	8.19
1.5200	1.5280	0.7365	0.7835	1.08
2.0266	1.6580	0.8065	1.2001	1.04×10^{-4}
3.3400	1.4710	0.6195	2.7205	8.98×10^{-4}

Although we cannot speak of the dissociation constant of hydrochloric acid, yet it is interesting to observe that the formula which is

derived only for weak acids is well applicable even for such a strong acid as hydrochloric acid and gives a constant value for K_2 which may be called the solubility constant for hydrochloric acid and with its help the solubility of an acid at any other concentration of the sodium chloride can be determined.

The following table gives the limit of applicability of solubility method for finding out the dissociation constant.

Acid used for finding K_2 .	Na salt used.	Range of Na salt investigated.	Value obtained for K_2 at 30°.	Real value for K_2 at 25°.	Limit of applicability.
Benzoic	Sodium formate	0·0N-2·4711N	$2·4 \times 10^{-4}$	$2·1 \times 10^{-4}$	All
Salicylic	„	0·0N-2·117N	$2·4 \times 10^{-4}$	$2·1 \times 10^{-4}$	All; strictly for intermediate conc.
Benzoic	Sodium acetate	0·0N-1·485N	$1·6 \times 10^{-5}$	$1·8 \times 10^{-5}$	All; strictly for high conc.
Salicylic	„	0·0N-1·610N	$1·8 \times 10^{-5}$	$1·8 \times 10^{-5}$	At high conc. only
Cinnamic	„	0·0N-1·610N	$2·4 \times 10^{-5}$	$1·8 \times 10^{-5}$	At high conc. only
Benzoic	Sodium citrate	0·0N-1·3989N	$2·2 \times 10^{-5}$	8×10^{-4}	Not applicable
Salicylic	„	0·0N-1·3989N	$5·5 \times 10^{-5}$	8×10^{-4}	Do
Cinnamic	„	0·0N-1·3989N	$1·8 \times 10^{-4}$	8×10^{-4}	Do
Cinnamic	Sodium benzoate	0·0N-0·800N	$6·65 \times 10^{-4}$	$6·4 \times 10^{-4}$	Applicable for intermediate conc.
Salicylic	„	0·0N-0·240N	$1·09 \times 10^{-3}$	$6·4 \times 10^{-3}$	Not applicable
Benzoic	Sodium salicylate	0·0N-1·825N	$1·0 \times 10^{-3}$	$1·0 \times 10^{-3}$	Applicable for intermediate conc.

It is thus clear that the formula is strictly true when K_1 and K_2 are very nearly of the same magnitude, as shown by theoretical considerations.

SUMMARY.

1. Dissociation constant of formic acid, acetic acid, salicylic, acid and citric acid, has been determined by the formula

$$K_2 = \frac{K_1 - a(c - b + a)}{(b - a)^2}$$

and the limit of concentration for which this equation holds has been thoroughly discussed.

2. It is shown that in some cases dissociation constant of the acid diminishes with the lowering of the concentration of its sodium salt and in some cases it increases with the dilution. It has been shown that two factors are acting in reverse way, hydrolysis of the salt and the degree of ionisation. With dilution degree of ionisation and hydrolysis increases but the former diminishes the number of acid molecules or $(b - a)$, while the latter increases the solubility, $(b - a)$. Thus when the former is increasing the value of dissociation constant the latter causes it to diminish and the observed result is due to one which is predominating.

3. The value of dissociation constant is greater when stronger acid is used for determining the value. This is explained on the basis of hydrolysis.

4. Various equilibria in solution of weak acid in solution of salt of weak acid have been discussed and their relationship studied. It is shown from these equations that the formula is applicable strictly when the dissociation constants of the acid investigated and employed are identical.

5. The above formula for finding the dissociation constant gives negative results with succinic acid. It is shown that Bhagwat and Dhar's general formula is applicable

$$K_n = \frac{nK - a(nc - b + a)}{(b - a)^2}$$

where n is the basicity of the acid employed, it being 2 in this case.

6. Although the formula is derived only for weak acids it is found to obey to some extent even for such a strong acid as hydrochloric acid.